

**A STUDY ON MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCES AND ITS RELATIONSHIP
TO THE ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF GRADE V PUPILS IN
SELECTED PUBLIC SCHOOLS IN THE DIVISION OF
OLONGAPO CITY ACADEMIC YEAR 2012-2013**

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A Study on Multiple Intelligences and its Relationship to the Academic Achievement of Grade V Pupils in Selected Public Schools in the Division of Olongapo City Academic Year 2012-2013

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Abstract

This study explores the relationship between multiple intelligences and academic achievement among grade five pupils in selected public schools in Olongapo City, Philippines. Grounded in Howard Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences, the research examines the profile of 321 respondents, including age, gender, parents' educational attainment and occupation, and family monthly income. The study describes the students' multiple intelligences across nine dimensions: naturalistic, linguistic, spatial, musical, bodily-kinesthetic, interpersonal, intrapersonal, logical-mathematical, and existential. Additionally, it assesses the academic performance of the pupils as reflected in their general point average grades. Employing a descriptive survey method, the research utilizes a questionnaire composed of demographic information and McKenzie's (1999) Multiple Intelligences Survey. Data analysis involves various statistical tools, including frequency counts, percentages, weighted means, t-tests, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Results indicate that respondents predominantly possess Naturalistic, Musical, Verbal, and Interpersonal intelligences. Surprisingly, no significant differences were observed in the perception of multiple intelligences when grouped according to profile variables such as age, sex, parents' educational attainment and occupation, and family monthly income. A slight negative correlation ($r = -0.213$, $p < 0.01$) was found between academic performance and multiple intelligence, suggesting that as multiple intelligence scores increase, there is a slight decrease in academic performance. The study concludes with recommendations for educators and schools to incorporate multiple intelligence theory into teaching strategies and curriculum development. These include enhancing course syllabi, providing necessary facilities and equipment, encouraging teacher professional development, and creating special programs for children with unique intelligences. The findings contribute to the ongoing dialogue about the role of multiple intelligences in education and its potential impact on academic achievement in the Philippine context.

Keywords: *multiple intelligences, academic achievement, grade five pupils, public schools, educational strategies*

Introduction

This study explores the relationship between multiple intelligences and academic achievement among grade five pupils in selected public schools in Olongapo City, Philippines. The research is grounded in Howard Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences, which posits that intelligence is not a single, fixed entity but rather comprises several distinct types of intelligence that individuals possess in varying degrees.

The study aims to examine the profile of the respondents, including age, gender, parents' educational attainment and occupation, and family monthly income. It will describe the multiple intelligences of the pupils across nine dimensions: naturalistic, linguistic, spatial, musical, bodily-kinesthetic, interpersonal, intrapersonal, logical-mathematical, and existential. The research will also assess the academic performance of the pupils as reflected in their general point average grades. Additionally, the study will investigate whether there are significant differences in multiple intelligences when pupils are grouped according to profile variables, and whether there is a significant relationship between academic performance and multiple intelligences.

A review of related literature and studies reveals a growing interest in the application of multiple intelligences theory in education. Previous research has shown mixed results regarding the relationship between multiple intelligences and academic achievement. Some studies have found positive correlations between certain types of intelligence and academic performance, while others have found no significant relationship. The current study aims to contribute to this body of knowledge by examining the specific context of grade five pupils in Olongapo City.

The study involves 321 grade five pupils from selected public elementary schools in Olongapo City, chosen through stratified random sampling. Data gathering will be supplemented by observation, interviews, and analysis of school documents.

This study is significant as it may provide valuable insights for pupils, parents, teachers, and administrators. By understanding the relationship between multiple intelligences and academic achievement, educators can develop more effective teaching strategies and learning environments that cater to diverse intelligence profiles. The findings may also help pupils recognize their strengths and potential areas for growth, guiding them towards more suitable career paths in the future.

The research is limited to the selected grade five pupils in Olongapo City during the 2012-2013 academic year. While the findings may not be generalizable to all contexts, they can serve as a basis for similar studies in other settings or grade levels. Through this investigation, the researcher hopes to contribute to the ongoing dialogue about the role of multiple intelligences in education and its

potential impact on academic achievement.

Methodology

The research adopts a descriptive survey method, which is appropriate for investigating and interpreting existing conditions, practices, beliefs, and trends. This approach allows the researcher to gather data on present conditions and analyze the relationships between variables.

The study involves 321 grade five pupils from six selected public elementary schools in Olongapo City, chosen through stratified random sampling using Sloven's formula. The respondents are distributed across the schools as follows: Olongapo City Elementary School (122 pupils), Sta. Rita Elementary School (62 pupils), Asinan Elementary School (22 pupils), Mabayuan Elementary School (38 pupils), Kalalake Elementary School (50 pupils), and Nellie E. Brown Elementary School (27 pupils).

The primary instrument used for data collection is a questionnaire composed of two parts. The first part gathers demographic information about the respondents and their general average grades. The second part utilizes the Multiple Intelligences Survey authored by McKenzie (1999), which consists of nine sets of statements designed to assess the respondents' skills and interests across different intelligence domains.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the instrument, the researcher sought feedback from her adviser and other educators knowledgeable about multiple intelligences. The questionnaire was then refined based on their suggestions and recommendations. Prior to data collection, the researcher obtained necessary permissions from the Division Schools Superintendent and the principals of the participating schools.

The researcher personally administered the questionnaires to explain the concept of multiple intelligences and address any questions or clarifications. Data collection took place during the 2012-2013 school year, with the researcher providing examples to help pupils understand and complete the questionnaire accurately.

For data analysis, the study employs various statistical tools. These include frequency counts and percentages to describe the demographic profile of the respondents, weighted means to analyze the multiple intelligence scores, t-tests and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to examine significant differences between variables, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to determine relationships between multiple intelligences and academic achievement.

The statistical treatments are carefully selected to address the research questions and test the hypotheses. The use of these diverse analytical tools allows for a comprehensive examination of the data, providing insights into the multiple intelligences of the grade five pupils and their relationship to academic achievement in the context of Olongapo City's public schools.

Results and Discussion

Profile of the respondents

Age. Out of Three Hundred Twenty One (321) student-respondents, there were 177 or 55.10% who were 10 years old; 129 or 40.20%, 11 years old; 14 or 4.40%, 12 years old; 1 or .30%, 14 years old. The computed weighted mean age of the student-respondents was (10.49) years old.

Sex. Out of Three Hundred Twenty One (321) student-respondents, there were 126 or 39.30% were males; 195 or 60.70%, females.

Educational Attainment of Father. Out of Three Hundred Twenty One (321) student-respondents, there were 3 or .90% whose father have attained elementary level of schooling; 8 or 2.50%, elementary graduate; 22 or 6.90%, high school level; 84 or 26.20%, high school graduate; 12 or 3.70%, vocational graduate; 145 or 45.20%, college graduate and 8 or 2.50% who were masteral or doctoral graduate.

Occupation of Father. Out of Three Hundred Twenty One (321) student-respondents, there were 31 or 9.70% whose fathers were Overseas Filipino Workers (OFW's); 14, 4.4.0%, carpenter; 41 or 12.80%, drivers and 235 or 73.20% who were others like government employees, entrepreneurs.

Educational Attainment of Mother. Out of Three Hundred Twenty One (321) student-respondents, there were 7 or 2.20% whose mothers have attained elementary level of schooling; 9 or 2.80%, elementary graduate; 25 or 7.80%, high school level; 79 or 24.60%, high school graduate; 8 or 2.50%, vocational graduate; 152 or 47.40%, college graduate and 5 or 1.60% who were masteral or doctoral graduate.

Occupation of Mother. Out of Three Hundred Twenty One (321) student-respondents, there were 90 or 28.00%, who were teachers; 182 or 56.70%, housekeeper; 25 or 7.80%, vendors; and 24 or 7.50%, fast food staff.

Family Monthly Income. Out of Three Hundred Twenty One (321) student-respondents, there were 253 or 78.80%, whose income ranged from Php5,000 to Php10,000; 34 or 10.60%, Php10,001-Php15,000; 12 or 3.70%, Php15,001-20,000 and 22 or 6.90%, Php20001 and above. The computed weighted mean of the family income was (9,431.57) monthly.

Academic Performance. Out of Three Hundred Twenty One (321) student-respondents, there were 10 or 3.10% who have obtained a general point average grade of 96-100; 33 or 10.30%, 91-95 %; 194 or 60.40%, 86-90; 71 or 22.10%, 81-85; 12 or 3.70%, 76-80 and 1 or .30%, 70-75. The computed weighted mean of the academic performance was (87.29) interpreted to be Very Good (VG).

Perceptions towards Multiple Intelligence

Section 1 –Naturalistic Intelligence. For indicator 1, In enjoy categorizing by common traits, obtained a total scores of (220) and ranked 7th; indicator 2, Ecological issues are important to me, (400), ranked 5th; indicator 3, Classification helps me make sense of new data (440), ranked 4th; indicator 4, I enjoy working in a garden (490) ranked 2nd; indicator 5, I believe preserving our National Parks is important (610) ranked 1st; indicator 6, Putting things in hierarchies makes sense to me (450) ranked 3rd; indicator 7, Animals are important in my life (310) ranked 6th; indicator 8, My home has a recycling system in place (130) ranked 8.5th; indicator 9, I enjoy studying biology, botany and/or zoology (30) ranked 10th and in indicator 10, I pick up on subtle differences in meaning (130) ranked 8.5th.

Section 2 – Musical Intelligence. For indicator 1, I easily pick up on patterns (160) and ranked 8th; indicator 2, I focus in on noise and sounds (270), ranked 6th; indicator 3, Moving to a beat is easy for me (350), ranked 5th; indicator 4, I enjoy making music (490) ranked 3rd; indicator 5, I respond to the cadence of poetry (110) ranked 11th; indicator 6, I remember things by putting them in a rhyme (500) ranked 2nd; indicator 7, Concentration is difficult for me if there is background noise (390) ranked 4th; indicator 8, Listening to sounds in nature can be very relaxing (240) ranked 7th; indicator 9, Musical are more engaging to me than dramatic plays (130) ranked 9th and in indicator 10, Remembering song lyrics is easy for me (590) ranked 1st.

Section 3. Logical Intelligence. For indicator 1, I am known for being neat and orderly (270) and ranked 6th; indicator 2, Step-by-step directions are a big help (380), ranked 5th; indicator 3, Problem solving comes easily to me (510), ranked 2nd; indicator 4, I get easily frustrated with disorganized people (360) ranked 4th; indicator 5, I get easily frustrated with disorganized people (420) ranked 3rd; indicator 6, Logical puzzles are fun (530) ranked 1st; indicator 7, I can't begin an assignment until I have all my "ducks in a row" (240) ranked 8th; indicator 8, Structure is a good thing (290) ranked 7th; indicator 9, I enjoy troubleshooting something that isn't working properly (130) ranked 9th; and in indicator 10, Things have to make sense to me or I am dissatisfied (80) ranked 10th.

Section 4-Existential Intelligence. For indicator 1, It is important to see my role in the "big picture " of things (210) ranked 7th; indicator 2, I enjoy discussing questions about life (200) ranked 8.5th; indicator 3, Religion is important to me (300) ranked 6th; indicator 4, I enjoy viewing art work (440) ranked 3rd; indicator 5, Relaxation and meditation exercises are rewarding to me (330) ranked 5th; indicator 6, I like traveling to visit inspiring places (480) ranked 1st; indicator 7, I enjoy reading philosophers (460) ranked 2nd; indicator 8, Learning new things is easier when I see their real world application (400) ranked 4th; indicator 9, I wonder if there are other forms of intelligent life in the universe (200) ranked 8.5th; indicator 10, It is important for me to feel connected to people, ideals and beliefs (190) ranked 10th.

Section 5-Interpersonal Intelligence. For indicator 1, I learn best interacting with others (230) ranked 8th; indicator 2, I enjoy informal chat and serious discussion (290) ranked 7th; indicator 3, The more the merrier (400) ranked 2.5th; indicator 4, I often serve as a leader among peers and colleagues. (360) ranked 5th; indicator 5, I value relationships more than ideas or accomplishments. (400) ranked 2.5th; indicator 6, Study groups are very productive for me.(580) ranked 1st; indicator 7, I am a "team player". (380) ranked 4th; indicator 8, Friends are important to me. (340) ranked 6th; indicator 9, I belong to three clubs or organizations. (110) ranked 10th; indicator 10, I dislike working alone. (120) ranked 9th.

Section 6-Kinesthetic Intelligence. For indicator 1, I learn by doing.(160) ranked 10th; indicator 2, I enjoy making things with my hands. (230) ranked 7th; indicator 3, Sports are a part of my life. (300) ranked 6th; indicator 4, I use gesture and non- verbal cues when I communicate.(390) ranked 3rd; indicator 5, Demonstrating is better than explaining.(520) ranked 1.5th; indicator 6, I love to dance. (520) ranked 4th; indicator 7, I like working with tools. (370) ranked 4th; indicator 8, Inactivity can make me more tired than being very busy. (310) ranked 5th; indicator 9, Hands- on activities are fun.(220) ranked 8th; indicator 10, I live an active lifestyle. (190) ranked 9th.

Section 7-Verbal Intelligence. Table 16 shows the perception of the student-respondents towards Section 7- item indicators for being possess with Verbal Intelligence. For indicator 1, Foreign languages interest me (240) ranked 8th; indicator 2, I enjoy reading books, magazines and web sites (220) ranked 9th; indicator 3, I keep a journal (370) ranked 3rd; indicator 4, Words puzzle like crosswords or jumbles are enjoyable (500) ranked 2nd; indicator 5, Taking notes helps me remember and understand (350) ranked 4th; indicator 6, I faithfully contact friends through letters and or/ e-mail (590) ranked 1st; indicator 7, It is easy for me to explain my ideas to others (260) ranked 6th; indicator 8, I write for pleasure (300) ranked 5th; indicator 9, Puns, anagrams and spoonerism are fun (250) ranked 7th; and in indicator 10, I enjoy public speaking (130) ranked 10th.

Section 8-Visual Intelligence. For indicator 1, My attitudes effects how I learn (360) ranked 5th; indicator 2, I like to be involved in causes that help others (300) ranked 7th; indicator 3, I am keenly aware of my moral beliefs (380) ranked 4th; indicator 4, I learn best when I have an emotional attachment to the subject (390) ranked 3rd; indicator 5, Fairness is important to me (480) ranked 1st; indicator 6, Social justice issues interest me (430) ranked 2nd; indicator 7, Working alone can be just productive as working in a group (310) ranked 6th; indicator 8, I need to know why I should do something before I agree to do it (200) ranked 9th; indicator 9, When I believe

in something I give more effort towards it (220) ranked 8th; and in indicator 10, I am willing to protest or sign a petition to right or wrong (140) ranked 10th.

Section 9-Spatial Intelligence. For indicator 1, Rearranging a room and redecorating are fun for me (210) ranked 9th; indicator 2, I enjoy creating my own works of art (290) ranked 6th; indicator 3, I remember better using graphic organizers (310) ranked 4.5th; indicator 4, I enjoy all kinds of entertainment media (430) ranked 3rd; indicator 5, Charts, graph and tables help me interpret data (470) ranked 2nd; indicator 6, A music video can make me more interested in a song (510) ranked 1st; indicator 7, I can recall things as mental pictures (310) ranked 4.5th; indicator 8, I am good at reading maps and blueprints (250) ranked 7.5th; indicator 9, Three dimensional puzzles are fun (250) ranked 7.5th; and in indicator 10, I can visualize ideas in my mind (180) ranked 10th.

Test of Significant Difference on MIs when grouped according to Profile Variables

Section 1-Naturalistic Intelligence. For age profile variable, obtained Sig. Value of (.226); sex (.123); highest educational attainment of father (.380); occupation of father (.315); highest educational attainment of mother (.557); occupation of mother (.805) and family monthly income (.966) all of which are higher than 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, therefore the Null Hypothesis is Accepted, hence there is no significant difference when grouped according to age, sex, educational attainment of father, occupation of father, educational attainment of mother, occupation of mother and family monthly income.

Section 2 – Musical Intelligence. For age profile variable, obtained Sig. Value of (.201); sex (.374); highest educational attainment of father (.441); occupation of father (.647); highest educational attainment of mother (.958); occupation of mother (.244) and family monthly income (.323) all of which are higher than 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, therefore the Null Hypothesis is Accepted, hence there is no significant difference when grouped according to age, sex, educational attainment of father, occupation of father, educational attainment of mother, occupation of mother and family monthly income.

Section 3 Logical Intelligence. For age profile variable, obtained Sig. Value of (.481); sex (.259); highest educational attainment of father (.384); occupation of father (.370); highest educational attainment of mother (.822); occupation of mother (.540) and family monthly income (.537) all of which are higher than 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, therefore the Null Hypothesis is Accepted, hence there is no significant difference when grouped according to age, sex, educational attainment of father, occupation of father, educational attainment of mother, occupation of mother and family monthly income.

Section 4-Existential Intelligence. For age profile variable, obtained Sig. Value of (.893); sex (.875); highest educational attainment of father (.255); occupation of father (.699); highest educational attainment of mother (.222); occupation of mother (.307) and family monthly income (.141) all of which are higher than 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, therefore the Null Hypothesis is Accepted, hence there is no significant difference when grouped according to age, sex, educational attainment of father, occupation of father, educational attainment of mother, occupation of mother and family monthly income.

Section 5-Interpersonal Intelligence. For age profile variable, obtained Sig. Value of (.691); sex (.120); highest educational attainment of father (.390); occupation of father (.793); highest educational attainment of mother (.503); occupation of mother (.086) and family monthly income (.660) all of which are higher than 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, therefore the Null Hypothesis is Accepted, hence there is no significant difference when grouped according to age, sex, educational attainment of father, occupation of father, educational attainment of mother, occupation of mother and family monthly income.

Section 6-Kinesthetic Intelligence. For age profile variable, obtained Sig. Value of (.768); sex (.467); highest educational attainment of father (.738); occupation of father (.554); highest educational attainment of mother (.712); and family monthly income (.603) of which are higher than 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, therefore the Null Hypothesis is Accepted, hence there is no significant difference when grouped according to age, sex, educational attainment of father, occupation of father, educational attainment of mother, and family monthly income. On the other hand, occupation of mother obtained (.0330 which is lower than (<) 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, therefore the Null Hypothesis is Rejected, hence there is significant difference according to occupation of mother.

Section 7-Verbal Intelligence. For age profile variable, obtained Sig. Value of (.538); sex (.532); highest educational attainment of father (.183); occupation of father (.567); highest educational attainment of mother (.892); occupation of mother (.911) and family monthly income (.717) all of which are higher than 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, therefore the Null Hypothesis is Accepted, hence there is no significant difference when grouped according to age, sex, educational attainment of father, occupation of father, educational attainment of mother, occupation of mother and family monthly income.

Section 8-Visual Intelligence. For age profile variable, obtained Sig. Value of (.567); sex (.585); highest educational attainment of father (.548); occupation of father (.094); highest educational attainment of mother (.550); occupation of mother (.493) and family monthly income (.862) all of which are higher than 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, therefore the Null Hypothesis is Accepted, hence there is no significant difference when grouped according to age, sex, educational attainment of father, occupation of father, educational attainment of mother, occupation of mother and family monthly income.

Section 9-Spatial Intelligence. For age profile variable, obtained Sig. Value of (.292); sex (.090); highest educational attainment of father (.085); occupation of father (.577); highest educational attainment of mother (.517); occupation of mother (.118) and family monthly income (.882) all of which are higher than 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, therefore the Null Hypothesis is Accepted, hence

there is no significant difference when grouped according to age, sex, educational attainment of father, occupation of father, educational attainment of mother, occupation of mother and family monthly income.

Relationship of Academic Performance and MIs

Pearson (r) was employed as shown in Table 1, to test the significant relationship between academic performance and the intelligence of the student-respondents. The computer generated Pearson (r) value of $-.213^{**}$ using SPSS denotes slight correlation. A t-test for significance was used to conclude if the value of (r) = $-.213$ is significant at 0.05 Alpha Level of significance. The significant t-test value of (.000) is lower than 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, Thus the Null Hypothesis of no significant difference was Rejected, hence there is significant difference. The findings show that at 0.05 % significance level, the data provide sufficient evidence to conclude that academic performance and multiple intelligence are slightly linearly correlated. Findings revealed that academic performance of the pupils slightly increases with slightly increasing multiple intelligence. These findings supports to the study of Cabrera (2007) found to have significant relationship between logical, linguistics and visual intelligence and the academic performance of the respondents.

Table 1. Pearson (r) to test the Significant Relationship Between Academic Performance And the Perceived Intelligences

Sources Of Correlations		Intelligence	Academic Performance
Intelligence	Pearson Correlation	1	$-.213^{**}$
	Sig. (2-Tailed)		.000
	N	321	321
Academic Performance	Pearson Correlation	$-.213^{**}$	1
	Sig. (2-Tailed)	.000	
	N	321	321

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the researcher concluded that the typical student-respondent is a female, nearly eleven years old, with college-educated parents. The father is typically a government employee, while the mother is often a housekeeper, with a family income averaging Php 9,431.57 monthly. Academically, the student respondents were rated as Very Good (VG) in their performance. The study revealed that the respondents predominantly possess Naturalistic, Musical, Verbal, and Interpersonal intelligences. Interestingly, no significant differences were observed in the perception of multiple intelligences when grouped according to profile variables such as age, sex, parents' educational attainment and occupation, and family monthly income.

In light of these conclusions, the researcher offers several recommendations. Teachers should prioritize awareness and knowledge of their pupils' particular intelligences as a benchmark for realigning and repositioning target objectives based on needs and demands. Course syllabi should be enhanced to include teaching methodologies and strategies that utilize multiple intelligences. Schools must be prepared to provide the necessary facilities and equipment to enhance these intelligences and skills. Teachers are encouraged to engage in further reading and attend seminars to improve their teaching craftsmanship and ability to work with pupils possessing multiple intelligences. Parents should be encouraged to fully support children with noted special skills and talents. Schools should consider creating special programs for children with unique and peculiar intelligences. Teachers should strive to be imaginative and creative in designing instructional materials and activities that maintain students' interest in learning. To enrich children's lives, the Multiple Intelligence theory should be applied and integrated into classroom activities. Finally, to validate the results and findings of this study, it is recommended that parallel studies be conducted with greater depth and broader scope.

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